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DEMONSTRATE UNDERSTANDING OF COURSE-BOOKS IN THE CLASSROOM

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ANNOTATION

In this article, explain how explain ways a course-book could be integrated into a course curriculum. Because they give teachers and students access to helpful pre-made content, course books continue to play an important role in EFL teaching and learning. On the other hand, improper usage of course materials can wear out students and degrade teachers. This paper explores the role of course books in EFL teaching and examines how teachers can make effective use of the material. It mainly applies to novice teachers and those working in centralized systems, where decisions are made by ministries and committees.

The purpose of course books, their influence on the teaching and learning processes, and the reasons for teaching course books-based, as opposed to course books-led, are discussed in the first section of the article. The article's second section is an try to illustrate the proper utilization of course books through the application of the critical stages of assessment, selection, adaptation, and supplementing. It also directs EFL teachers to resources for direction and useful counsel.

Key words: *course-book, committees, integrate, curriculum, stimulate, activity, materials, centralized, skill, learner, prediction, approach, analyze, features, layout, communicative.*

During the explaining of ways a course-book could be integrated into a course curriculum. There are several ways that a course-book could be used (or not

used) when creating a course curriculum. Name two ways and explain what they are and how they work.

1. Using and integrating a course book into a course curriculum can be beneficial for both school administration and the teacher. Therefore, the Administration should be thoughtful for selecting cutting-edge textbooks and using them in an adapted way to local context. For example, Headway fourth edition for all levels, and the contents are suitable to the plan of the school curriculum. The Headway textbook meets our school criteria including extra digital version of the textbook. Through access to digital account of Headway textbook students can be benefitted by doing extra activities as and they can retain the learned material better.

2. The next approach is an in-house scheme of work that has no course-book but alternatively, they may use a different websites as supplementary material. This costs extra expense for the school budget and several websites are payable to subscribe. Engaging materials on British Council BC websites can be much more update materials, relevant and age- appropriate. Besides that, user- friend list, visually stimulating activities can make the learners hone the best practice of the content. For instance, the activity banks, vocabulary banks can be used for the independent study of students in make-up classes for low-level students teachers can recommend the websites and display on the class screen how to use them by providing guidelines.

Analyze the main features of commonly used EFL course-books

1). Course book 1:

Analysis of features: Open Mind pre-intermediate. Authors: Mickey Rogers, Joanne Taylor Knowles, Steve Taylor Knowles by Macmillan publication. The layout of the course-book is enabling students to interact effectively in the English language through developing 4 skills, in addition to developing critical thinking skills. The Life skills section is a totally new section that divides into three domains incorporating Self and Society, Work and Career, and study and learning which promotes 21st-century soft learning skills. The course-book caters to different learner styles and multiple intelligences. The unit opener activity pictures are good for visual learners, and listening activities and video extracts can facilitate auditory learners, the role- plays, tables, graphic organizers concept maps, board – games foster kinesthetic learners needs. A wide range of activities starting wrap- up language and speaking workshop, writing workshop, and reading and listening activities helps to enhance 4 skills of the target language. Emphasizing pair work and group work activities enhance learners' discussion skills and higher-order thinking skills that textbook activities facilitate language learning in a meaningful way. Language learners can make rapid progress if they use this course-book. The course-book provides in–depth materials and resources for mastering a language teaching via communicative competence.

2) Course-book 2:

Analysis of features: New Headway Fourth edition. Authors: John and Liz Soars by Oxford University Press publication.

The layout of the textbook is user-friendly. New language is introduced systematically, allowing a student to extend and consolidate their knowledge of the language. Listening material is provided in 3 CDs. New vocabulary is introduced regularly followed by controlled practice, allowing the student to use the language immediately

in a supported way. The course-book consists Teacher's book (TB) Student book (SB) workbook with I checker.

The course-book covers all 4 skills speaking combined with listening and reading combined with writing. The Course-book has a digital version too where the teacher can have access to Unit tests, skills tests, and progress tests. The digital book has additional printable materials, video materials, and video worksheets.

The Course-book caters to all different types of learners starting a Starter activity engages visual learners and activates students' schemata, the next follow-up activity starts with a reading task that reinforces input to the learner and the rest skills come in a sequencing way and helps the learner to retain the information in a consolidated way. Auditory learners can benefit from listening activities and listening and filling in the blanks, listening to conversations can engage auditory learners. Kinesthetic learners can benefit from practicing conversations with a partner and role-play activities.

The course-book one unit organization empowers a wide range of tasks, including 4 skills, a practice part, a vocabulary part, and an Everyday English part.

Students can practice the language in formal and informal settings and the book facilitates Communicative language teaching.

Describe the benefits/drawbacks of using digital versus physical course-books:

Digital resources of a course-book can provide extra opportunities for learners. The range of online and downloadable components allows blended learning which is needed in the 21st century.

The practice of digital course-books promotes learner Autonomy/Automatic marking can provide a chance to practice the language and gain the best experience.

The main drawback of the course-book is that regular access to the internet. In remote places, the internet connection is not stable. In addition, the awareness of computer literacy is crucial for our students, students should know how to register for digital course-books and activate the code using their Google account.

List of used literature.

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